

elimination of benzylamine in presence of base affords III as shown in Chart 1.

Chart 1

The oxazolone structure assigned to these products has support from elemental analysis, ir, nmr and mass spectra. IR spectrum of III_a showed bands at 1750 and 1670 cm⁻¹ indicative of carbonyl group and C=N linkage, respectively. NMR spectrum of III_b showed three methyl protons as a singlet at 7.7 τ and nine aromatic protons as a multiplet between 2.2 to 2.8 τ. In mass spectra, molecular ion peaks constituted the base peaks. Mass and nmr spectra further indicated that acylation of OH and NH₂ groups also took place under the reaction conditions.

The products (Table 1) are found to be identical (m.m.p.) with the authentic samples of the respective oxazolones synthesized by an unambiguous route⁴.

TABLE 1—2-PHENYL-4-(α-METHYLBENZAL)-5-OXAZOLONES (III)

Compound	R	m.p.* °C	Yield %
III _a	p-OC ₂ H ₅	37	70
III _b	p-Cl	250	80
III _c	p-OCOCH ₃	100	75
III _d	m-NO ₂	70	80
III _e	p-CH ₃	167	80
III _f	p-NHCOCH ₃	143	75
III _g	o,p-Br ₂	138	70
III _h	o,p-(OCOCH ₃) ₂	153	70

*All melting points are uncorrected.
All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

The above oxazolones (III_a-III_h) along with 2-phenyl-4-(α-methylbenzal)-5-oxazolone (III_i) and 2-phenyl-4-(α-methyl-p-bromobenzal)-5-oxazolone (III_j) were tested for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria solani*, *Colletotrichum capsici* and *Choanephora cucurbitarum* by poisoned food technique. For each compound three concentrations viz. 1000, 500 and 250 ppm were tried. Compounds III_b, III_d, III_f, III_g and III_h completely inhibited all the three fungi at 1000 ppm. The other five compounds were not so effective even at 1000 ppm. A detailed study of the structure activity relationship showed that the presence of Cl, NO₂ and NHCOCH₃ groups in phenyl ring of oxazolone increased the activity of unsubstituted oxazolone III_i. Another interesting feature of the study was that while the presence of one Br or OCOCH₃ in the phenyl ring had little effect on the activity, presence of two Br or two OCOCH₃ in the phenyl ring (III_g and III_h) made these oxazolones the most effective.

Experimental

Reaction of azlactone with α-methyl-p-chlorobenzal-benzylamine: Hippuric acid (1.8 g) and α-methyl-p-chlorobenzalbenzylamine (0.01 mole) were dissolved in dry benzene (50 ml). Acetic anhydride (1.2 ml) and sodium acetate (0.5 g) were added to the solution. The mixture was just heated to get a clear solution and left at room temperature for 2 days. During this period most of the product precipitated which was filtered off. The mother liquor on concentration gave more of the product. The product was recrystallized from hot benzene, m.p. 250° (yield 80%). Other oxazolones were synthesized in similar manner.

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Amoebicidal Testing of Drugs—Use of Goat Serum as a Substitute for Horse Serum for Growing *Entamoeba histolytica*

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A MOEBIASIS is one of the most prevalent diseases in tropical countries like India. Unfortunately, even today, the disease is not diagnosed adequately and critically though prolonged amoebiasis causes ulcerations, hepatic complications, liver

abscess and other associated diseases. It is, however, well established that an ideal antiameobic agent should be capable of eradicating the causative organism *Entamoeba histolytica* both from the bowel and from extra intestinal sites at non-toxic doses^{1,2}. Though a number of useful drugs have been synthesised, they are not found to be universally effective or ideal and are usually associated with side effects. Moreover, need for drugs with sustained prophylactic actions are widely felt³. But no single preparation satisfy all these requirements.

In our attempt to study the synthesis of new antiameobic drugs based on the physico-chemical properties of different known antiameobic drugs and their biological properties, it has been found necessary to screen the different antiameobic agents in the laboratory by proper *in vitro* testing.

E. histolytica is generally grown in Boeck and Drbohlav medium consisting of egg slant of horse serum overlay with bacteria plus rice starch. In view of high cost of horse serum and the difficulty in obtaining its regular supply, Dutta⁴ used bovine serum as a substitute for growing *E. histolytica*. However, availability of goat serum is comparatively easy in Kalyani and we prefer to use goat serum as a substitute for horse serum.

We report in this communication our attempt to use goat serum as a substitute for horse serum or bovine serum for growing *E. histolytica*, and to standardize and test the method by using some known antiameobicides and screen a few unknown compounds. Study of amoebicidal properties of drugs in different media would be helpful in comparing amoebicidal action of antiameobic drugs against axenically grown *E. histolytica* and in different medium using horse, bovine or goat serum

Experimental

Preparation of serum : For the preparation of serum and screening of drugs, we followed the same procedure as reported by Dutta *et al.*^{5,6}. Fresh goat blood was collected from Kalyani market in a thermoflask. The serum was decanted, centrifuged at 2000 rpm for about half an hour and filtered through sintered glass filter. The filtered serum was taken in a clean dry sterilised conical flask, inactivated in a thermostat at 56° for about 1 hr and stored at 4°. The stored serum was diluted eight fold with 0.85% normal saline in M/40 phosphate buffer (pH=7.0) before use.

Technique of cultivation : A series of test tubes and Erlenmeyer flasks were thoroughly cleaned, dried, plugged with cotton and sterilised at 150° for 1 hr in an air-oven. 8 eggs (Hen) were thoroughly cleansed with detergent and subsequently sterilized with alcohol. The eggs were broken and the contents emulsified with M/40 phosphate buffer and filtered through a sintered glass filter. Different strains of *E. histolytica* were grown in the flasks with diluted goat serum, mixed bacterial flora and rice starch at 37°. Sub-cultures were made every

48 hr. 5 ml of emulsified egg solution was poured in each of the sterilised test tubes placed at an angle of 45° and heated at 80° for 1 hr in an air-oven. The heating was repeated thrice in succession. The appearance of turbidity in the contents of the medium indicated lack of proper sterilization and caused immediate rejection. *E. histolytica* was cultured in these test tubes. 0.2% solutions of acriflavin and gentian violet were used to prevent overgrowth of fungal and bacterial flora.

Isolation of strain of *E. histolytica* : LD strain of *E. histolytica* was isolated from fresh stool samples collected from Usha 'X'-ray clinic, P. O. Ranaghat, Nadia. Both trophozite and cystic forms of *E. histolytica* were present. The sample was washed with 0.85% NaCl solution and transferred into goat serum medium. This was repeated several times and the contents were examined under the microscope (10X-90X). Trophozite form of *E. histolytica* was collected in this way and preserved. Strain collected from the School of Tropical Medicine, Calcutta, was also used.

TABLE 1—*In vitro* ACTIVITIES OF AMOEBICIDAL DRUGS

Drugs	Amoebicidal concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) 48 hr
Enteroquinol	62.5
Enteroviaform	62.5
Diiodoquinol	500.00
Chloroquine-phosphate	500.00
Metronidazole	7.81
5-Chloro-7-nitro-8-hydroxy quinoline ⁺	15.6
Emetine hydrochloride	7.81
Glycobiarsol	500.00
Furanidazole	62.5
Clephamide	62.5
6-Amino-5-spiro-(4,5)-decane/hydrochloride ⁺	15.6
1-n-Butyl-3,4-dimethoxy-5-amino-5,6,7,8,9-pentahydro-benzocyclo heptene/hydrochloride ⁺	62.5
1-n-Butyl-3,4-dimethoxy-5-dimethyl amino-5,6,7,8,9-pentahydro-benzocyclo heptene/hydrochloride ⁺	250.00

⁺ The compounds were synthesised by Prof. B. C. Pathak *et al.*, Department of Applied Chemistry, University of Calcutta. The other drugs were procured from The Central Drug Laboratory, Calcutta and from Prof. B. C. Pathak.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF AMOEBICIDAL ACTIVITIES ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) REPORTED BY VARIOUS WORKERS

	Philips ^v	Nakamora and Anderson ^o	Bradner and Rawson ^o	Diamond and Bartgis ^{1o}	Dutta and Yadava ⁴	Present study
Strain of <i>E. histolytica</i>	F-22	F-22	F-22	F-22	NIH 200	LD 1
Period of incubation with drug	48 and 72 hr	48 hr	48 hr	72 hr	72 hr	48 and 72 hr
Emetine-hydrochloride	5	10	31.2	6	11.7	7.8* (3.9-7.8*)
Metronidazole	—	—	—	0.75-1.5	3.9	3.9-7.8*
Enterovioform	—	40-50	125	—	31.2	62.5
Chloroquine phosphate	—	—	—	—	1000	500
Diiodoquine	—	200	1000	—	375	500

Upper limit (3.9-7.8—activity is observed within these limits)

Examination and sub-culture of *E. histolytica* : Four day old cultures were examined under an inverted microscope (10X ocular and 20X objective) and the tubes showing $20-30 \times 10^4$ amoebae/ml were used as seed for sub-culturing fresh tubes. For sub-culture, 0.2 ml of this amoebic suspension was inoculated into each tube containing 8.8 ml of the medium and the cultures were incubated vertically at 37°.

Drug testing : Most of the drugs are insoluble in water. Some of the drugs are dissolved in a little DMF solution. In general, fine suspensions of drug were made by adding gum acacia. 1 ml of drug suspension in normal saline (10 mg/ml) was added to each culture tube containing 9 ml inoculated medium (8.8 ml medium+0.2 ml inoculum) in duplicate to give a drug concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ per tube. Each tube contained 23.75×10^4 amoebae/ml. Successive two-fold serial dilutions (eight) of the drug in sterile normal saline was added in subsequent duplicate tubes. Strict aseptic conditions were maintained. Drug suspensions were sterilized by autoclaving at 10 lb/sq inch for 15 min at 120°. The tests were run for 72 hr (though 48 hr are sufficient) and incubation was carried out at 37°. Amoebicidal end point was examined on the basis of presence or absence of living amoebae by direct observation under a microscope and by sub-culture.

The operations were repeated to examine the reproductibility of the results. The results of some known and unknown drugs are recorded in Table 1.

In vitro activities of antiamoebic drugs against *E. histolytica* have been widely reported^{4 10}. Variations of end points depending on conditions are also noted.

Discussions

The results presented in the Table 1 and Table 2 show that goat serum can be successfully utilised instead of horse serum for the culture of *E. histolytica*. The results also show that all the unknown compounds particularly spiroamino

hydrochloride and 5-chloro-7-nitro-hydroxyquinoline can be successfully used as antiamoebic drugs. Spiroamino hydrochloride and its derivatives should receive special attention as amoebicidal properties of these compounds are not yet reported.

It will be quite pertinent to compare some of results with those reported earlier (Table 2). Slight variations in results appear reasonable in view of different strains and culture media. Furthermore, insolubility of the drugs poses a big problem and variations of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) appear natural. We have reported the upper limits of MIC taking into consideration all these limitations.

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